

THE ROLE OF PHARMACOVIGILANCE IN COMBATTING DRUG RELATED ADVERSE EVENTS

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ABSTRACT

Pharmacovigilance plays a pivotal role in identifying, evaluating, and mitigating drug-related adverse events (ADEs), thereby ensuring patient safety and drug efficacy. As drugs are administered to diverse populations in real-world settings, unanticipated adverse reactions can arise, which may not have been detected during pre-market clinical trials. Pharmacovigilance systems are designed to monitor these reactions continuously post-market, capturing data from various sources such as clinical reports, electronic health records, and patient feedback.

The process involves systematic collection and analysis of data on adverse drug reactions (ADRs), followed by risk assessment and communication of findings to healthcare professionals and regulatory authorities. Through this vigilant oversight, pharmacovigilance helps in identifying potential safety issues early, facilitating timely intervention to mitigate risks. This includes issuing warnings, updating drug labels, or even withdrawing unsafe products from the market. Furthermore, pharmacovigilance contributes to improving drug development processes by providing insights into the safety profiles of drugs, which can guide future research and development.

The integration of advanced technologies, such as big data analytics and artificial intelligence, enhances the effectiveness of pharmacovigilance by enabling more accurate and rapid detection of ADEs. Overall, pharmacovigilance is crucial for protecting public health, optimizing therapeutic outcomes, and maintaining the trust of patients and healthcare providers in the pharmaceutical industry. Its ongoing evolution is essential to address emerging safety challenges and ensure the safe use of medications in diverse populations. "This review explores the pivotal role of pharmacovigilance in detecting, assessing, and mitigating drug-related adverse events, highlighting its impact on patient safety, regulatory practices, and drug development.

Key Words: Pharmacovigilance, Adverse events, Drug efficacy, Clinical trials, Artificial intelligence.

Introduction:

Pharmacovigilance is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the science and practices connected to the identification, evaluation, comprehension, and avoidance of side effects or any other drug-related issue. The World Bank provided funding for the National Pharmacovigilance Programme (NPVP) until 2009, when it was renamed the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI). India is becoming a center for clinical trials and the creation of new pharmaceuticals due to scientific and technological advancements, which presents a challenge to the monitoring of safety issues with the use of new drugs. Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) that affect patients because of polypharmacy, over-the-counter (OTC) medication use, physician changes, etc. have shown to be challenging to detect or monitor. Because of this, the national program has recently become more significant in our nation. However, it is noted that not all medical experts understand the significance of this program. Therefore, it would be crucial to raise health care workers' awareness through various channels and faculty development programs in order to support and strengthen the national program that aims to identify, report, and analyze the identified adverse drug reactions ADRs. (1)

Historical Background Evolution

The Greek word "pharmakon" (drug) and the Latin word "vigilance" (to keep watch) are combined to get the term "pharmacovigilance". (2) Since numerous Asian nations joined the Uppsala Monitoring Centre in 1998 to enhance the detection of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) through spontaneous reporting, pharmacovigilance has gained significance in the region. (3)

pharmacovigilance began 169 years ago, on January 29, 1848, when Hannah Greener, a little girl from the north of England, passed away following the administration of a chloroform anesthesia prior to the extraction of an infected toenail. (4)

Diethyl glycol, a solvent used in sulphanilamide elixir, was unknown to be poisonous at the time and was blamed for 107 deaths in the USA in 1937. (4,5,6) The Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act of 1938 resulted from this, permitting factory inspections and requiring proof of drug safety prior to approval. (7)

Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) was not recommended for patients with ulcers due to Douthwaite's 1938(8) suggestion that it can cause gastrointestinal bleeding. This danger was later validated in 1955. (9) Significant reforms in European pharmacovigilance were prompted by the 1961 Thalidomide disaster, which was connected to congenital deformities. (10) The UK implemented the "Yellow Card" system for reporting drug toxicity in 1964 as a result of Drs. McBride and Lenz's identification of the hazards associated with thalidomide. (11) Another consequence of this catastrophe was the European Community Directive 65/65, which improved drug safety laws in 1965. (12)

In-hospital monitoring to investigate drug adverse effects was first implemented in 1966 with the launch of the Boston Collaborative Drug Surveillance Program. (13) Italy joined the WHO's International Drug Monitoring Program in 1975 after eleven other nations participated in it in 1968. (14) After thalidomide's association with congenital abnormalities was shown by a 1973 study, spontaneous adverse drug response reporting became organized and controlled. (15)

Fig 1: Historical background Evolution

Pharmacovigilance Systems and Frameworks

Pharmacovigilance Systems and Regulations on a Global and Regional Scale

1. Worldwide Networks

- WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION (WHO)-Uppsala

Function: Offers worldwide pharmacovigilance activity coordination.

Principal Duties: Gathers and evaluates ADR information, facilitates national pharmacovigilance initiatives, and offers instruction.

The International Drug Monitoring Program aims to enhance drug safety by promoting global cooperation and data exchange. (17)

- International Guidelines for Pharmacovigilance:

Focus: Ensure that risk management, signal detection, and ADR reporting procedures are standardized internationally. (16) Key documents: The function of country centers in WHO's global drug monitoring program.

- Global Harmonization Conference (ICH) E2E Pharmacovigilance Guidelines: The scope establishes the conditions that must be met for ADR gathering, evaluation, and reporting.

Content: Stresses the value of regular safety update reports (PSURs) and proactive risk management.

Updates: Updates to ICH E2E for clinical trials and post-marketing surveillance have resulted in ICH E6 (R2) and ICH E2D

Good Clinical Practice (GCP), ICH E6 (R2):

Incorporation: Contains specifications for pharmacovigilance in clinical trials with an emphasis on risk management and safety reporting. (16)

2. Localized Frameworks

➤ European Medicines Agency (EMA) of the European Union (EU):

Committee for Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment (PRAC):

Function: Assesses safety signals, evaluates and keeps track of medication safety, and offers suggestions for reducing risk.

Reports: communicates risks and provides periodic safety update reports, or PSURs.

(EU) Regulation No. 1235/2010:

Important requirements include the creation of risk management plans (RMPs), the meticulous reporting of ADRs, and the stringent observance of deadlines for reporting major ADRs. marketing authorization holders (MAHs) are required to have effective pharmacovigilance procedures in place.

European Harmonized Reports, or EHR:

Standardization: Consistent and precise data gathering amongst member nations is made possible by uniform standards for ADR reporting and data submission. (16)

➤ United States :The Food and Drug Administration (FDA)

Healthcare providers and patients can report adverse events through the MedWatch Program, which gathers and tracks ADR data.

Documentation Needed: Timelines for reporting non-serious occurrences vary, but serious ADRs need to be notified within 15 calendar days.

21 CFR Section 314:

Rules: Defines the obligations of medication producers and the conditions for ADR reporting, along with providing comprehensive submission criteria.

Measures of Risk Assessment and Reduction (REMS):

The goal is employs risk management techniques to guarantee that certain medications with recognized hazards are used in a safe manner. (17,18)

➤ Japan: Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency, (PMDA)

Accountabilities: oversees pharmacovigilance and drug safety, necessitating thorough risk management strategies and ADR reporting.

Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting: Requires frequent submission of safety updates and prompt reporting of significant ADRs.

➤ Law Concerning Pharmaceutical Affairs:

Regulations: Specifies the parameters for post-marketing surveillance and ADR reporting, as well as the framework for drug safety monitoring. (17,18)

➤ The India Pharmaceutical Vigilance Programme (PvPI):

Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) is in charge of management.

Key duties: oversees ADRs, does safety evaluations, and offers risk management advice. The Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, Schedule Y Requirements: outlines post-marketing surveillance and clinical trial pharmacovigilance procedures, including ADR reporting schedules and risk assessment procedures. (17,18)

➤ Clinical Goods Administration (TGA) of Australia:

Health care providers' and customers' adverse event reports are gathered and assessed by the Adverse Event Reporting System (AERS).

Rules: demands the filing of recurring safety reports and the reporting of significant ADRs.

➤ Prescription Medicine Regulations in Australia (ARGPM):

Recommendations: Describe the conditions for pharmacovigilance, such as ADR reporting, risk sharing, and risk mitigation techniques. (18)

Pharmacovigilance is necessary

1. It can be necessary to track a drug's effects both during and after clinical trials and once it hits the market.
2. Adverse occurrences may occur both during clinical trials and following the product's release into the market.
3. Check the medication's quality.
4. Recognize the health hazards connected to the use of specific medications.
5. Keep individuals safe.

6. Study the effectiveness of medications. (20)

Why do we need Pharmacovigilance?

Fig 2: Need for Pharmacovigilance

Adverse Drug Reactions:

Different from side effects, adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are negative effects of medication that happen at regular dosages. In pharmacovigilance, assessing adverse drug reactions (ADRs) is essential to guarantee medication safety and patient safety. (21)

➤ Spontaneous reporting system

1. Regionalization
2. Repossession of further data
3. Access to all important pre and post marketing information
4. Detailed drug utilization data.
5. Standardized Evaluation of causality and significance
6. Encouragement

➤ Documentation of adverse drug reactions`

The global pharmacovigilance curriculum encourages the documentation of all suspected adverse drug-related events. It shows interest in the following reports:

- (A) Any side effect that new medications and medications with current issues may have, suspected or actual.
- (B) Records of different medications that resulted in adverse drug reactions (ADRs), such as fatalities, life-threatening illnesses, impairments, hospital stays, and congenital abnormalities.

It is recommended that any notable side effect from a medication be reported within seven days. Within eight days, additional adverse event details should be recorded. Any pharmacovigilance center can provide ADR forms, which can then be obtained and submitted to a peripheral center. Following evaluation, the form is sent from the peripheral center to the regional center, which subsequently transfers it to the zonal center. After statistical analysis, the information is forwarded to the WHO-Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC). (22)

➤ Process for Notifying ADRs

What to Report: Medication overdoses and pharmaceutical flaws, as well as any suspected adverse drug reactions (ADRs).

Physicians, pharmacists, nurses, and all other hospital employees (public and private) are eligible to report.

When to Report: Whenever a negative response is observed.

How to Report: Fill out the yellow ADR form entirely.

Where to Report: Send the Pharmacovigilance Program of India (PvPI) the completed ADR form.

➤ **Monitoring adverse drug reactions**

ADR monitoring is monitoring and evaluating medication side effects on a regular basis. A key component of this procedure is pharmacovigilance. It is the duty of pharmaceutical regulators to inspect products and document any possible bad reactions. Drugs, herbal remedies, cosmetics, medical equipment, and biological products can all result in adverse drug reactions. Good ADR monitoring helps reduce the negative effects of therapeutic items while ensuring that patients receive safe and effective treatment.

Fig 3:Trends of pharmacovigilance⁽⁴⁰⁾

➤ **Advantages of ADR Surveillance**

The following advantages can be obtained with an ADR monitoring and reporting program:

1. It provides information about the safety and quality of pharmaceutical goods.
2. It starts planning for risk management.
3. It assists in calculating the incidence of ADRs and avoids the predictable negative effects.
4. It raises awareness of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and provides information about them to patients, pharmacists, nurses, and the health care team.

ADR monitoring's primary goals are to reveal the kind and frequency of ADRs as well as to pinpoint the risk factors that may result in negative reactions.⁽²³⁾

Classical Examples of Serious and Unexpected Adverse Reactions⁽²⁴⁾

MEDICINE	ADVERSE REACTION
Aminophenazone (amidopyrine)	Agranulocytosis
Chloramphenicol	Aplastic anaemia
Clioquinol	Myelo-optic neuropathy (SMON)
Erythromycin estolate	Cholestatic hepatitis
Fluothane	Hepatocellular hepatitis
Methyldopa	Haemolytic anaemia
Oral contraceptives	Thromboembolism
Practolol	Sclerosing peritonitis
Reserpine	Depression
Statins	Rhabdomyolysis
Thalidomide	Congenital malformations

Role of Pharmacovigilance in Drug Safety

In order to meet the growing demands for safety and openness, drug safety monitoring encompasses a network of stakeholders, including the general public, legislators, and health experts. Effective management of safety issues is ensured by pharmacovigilance programs that are enhanced by strong connections with regulators. In order to effectively manage risks and safeguard the public's health, cooperation is crucial.

Fig 4: Pharmacovigilance & Drug Safety⁽⁴¹⁾

- **Clinical trial Regulation:** Regulatory organizations are focusing on the safety and efficacy of new goods due to the increase in clinical trials conducted worldwide. Coordinating data amongst national pharmacovigilance centers, educating medical personnel, and incorporating medication safety into clinical practice all contribute to effective patient care. This ongoing dialogue aids in identifying knowledge gaps about illnesses brought on by medication. ⁽¹⁾
- **Post Marketing Safety Drug Monitoring:** This includes tracking drug residues in animals, identifying drug interactions, evaluating the effects of medications on the environment, assessing the safety of inactive substances, and comparing the safety profiles of similar medications. The methodical approach to benefit-risk assessment of medications after marketing has been improved by the (The Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences) CIOMS report. ⁽³¹⁾
- **Pharmacovigilance in National Drug Policy:** The effective, safe, and high-quality use of medications is the responsibility of national governments. Establishing a national medicine regulatory body and an adverse reaction study center are essential for this. Effective pharmacotherapy education and monitoring require cooperation between health agencies, universities, NGOs, the pharmaceutical business, and professional groups.
- **Pharmacovigilance in Disease Control Public Health Programmes:** It is especially important to monitor medication safety when treating diseases like malaria, HIV/AIDS, and tuberculosis in places without regulatory frameworks or adequate healthcare facilities. Countries with public health disease control programs ought to give priority to pharmacovigilance. ⁽¹⁾
- **Drug use:** Patterns of drug use play a significant role in determining drug safety. For example, developing nations use injectable medications more frequently. In many nations, direct marketing of prescription drugs to consumers has been the norm. ⁽³²⁾ With this knowledge, people feel more equipped to choose their own treatments on their own, without the help of a physician or pharmacist. As a result, there has been a rise in overprescribing by physicians in response to patient requests, as well as the legal and illegal sale of medications online. This has significantly impacted the rise in prescriptions. ^(33,34)

- **Detection of Adverse Effects: Monitoring:** Data on adverse drug reactions (ADRs) is gathered and analyzed by pharmacovigilance systems from a variety of sources, such as retrospective reports, patient feedback, and clinical trials.
- **Reporting Systems:** Manufacturers, patients, and medical professionals notify regulatory agencies of any suspected side effects. These reports are then analyzed for trends or signals that might point to any safety concerns. (25,26)

Risk and Benefit Evaluation:

- **Analysis of the Data:** The frequency, seriousness, and possible influence of negative effects are evaluated by analyzing the collected data. Knowing if a drug's advantages continue to exceed its drawbacks is made easier by this.
- **Risk Evaluation:** Teams responsible for pharmacovigilance evaluate safety signals to see if they point to novel or unanticipated dangers.
- **Risk Management: Preventive Actions:** Pharmacovigilance may result in suggestions for extra safety measures, modifications to medication labels, dose adjustments, or use limitations based on risk assessments. The process of minimizing risks that have been discovered through the development of strategies such as risk communication plans or the requirement for risk evaluation and mitigation strategies (REMS).

Pharmacovigilance Case Management Workflow:

Fig 5 : Pharmacovigilance process work flow(42)

- **Impact on Public Health: Patient Safety:** Pharmacovigilance's ultimate goal is to safeguard patients by making sure that medications are taken as directed and that the likelihood of negative drug responses is decreased.
- **Making Informed Decisions:** Giving patients and healthcare professionals access to current safety data so they may make knowledgeable choices about drug use. (26)

EXAMPLES

Adverse Drug Reactions: The Example of Thalidomide

Thalidomide has been widely used as a supposedly safe treatment for nausea and morning sickness since its release in 1957. It was soon linked to a congenital disorder that caused the children of pregnant women using this medicine to be born with severe birth defects. By 1965, thalidomide had been banned in the majority of countries. Nevertheless, it continued to be used to treat leprosy, and more recently, its list of indications was expanded to include a far wider spectrum of illnesses. These applications are only allowed under strict supervision and expert advice. Despite these precautions, 34 cases of thalidomide embryopathy were

documented in leprosy endemic regions of South America between 1969 and 1995 by the Latin American Collaborative Study of Congenital Malformations. (27, 28)

Pharmacovigilance in practice: the example of cerivastatin

Cerivastatin was first approved as a medicine to control cholesterol in 1997. By 2000, 549 cases of rhabdomyolysis associated with cerivastatin usage had been reported to the WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring in Uppsala, Sweden. Consequently, a caution was issued on a potential correlation between myopathy, rhabdomyolysis, and cerivastatin. A contraindication for taking cerivastatin with gemfibrozil, another lipid-regulating drug, was added to prescription information in November 1999 in the US and March 2000 in Canada. In February 2001, Australia took similar action and sent a notification to prescribers regarding the possibility that all statins could result in rhabdomyolysis. In June 2001, a European-wide regulatory action was put into place to forbid the simultaneous administration of cerivastatin and gemfibrozil.

Malaria: an example of pharmacovigilance in public health

Many countries are currently treating malaria with combinations of multiple artemisinin derivatives as first- and second-line therapy due to the increasing resistance to conventional antimalarial drugs. The move toward artemisinin combination therapies (ACTs) has made it possible to develop pharmacovigilance systems in countries that did not previously have formal procedures in place to monitor the safety of drugs. The 2003 training's objective was to teach participants from five African countries the principles of drug safety monitoring with the aim of assisting in the introduction of a standard system of pharmacovigilance for new antimalarial medicines. Since then, two of these countries have made significant progress in antimalarial medication monitoring, and the other three have established official pharmacovigilance facilities.(30)

Challenges in Pharmacovigilance

- **Globalization:** Due to globalization, a greater number of people have access to a wider range of medications, including those for pandemic illnesses. Benefits aside, this permits unregulated international trade as well as the extensive and frequently inaccurate distribution of drug-related data, including that regarding illegal, regulated, and spurious medications.
- **Broader Safety Concerns:** Pharmacovigilance today includes problems including overdosing, interactions, polypharmacy, inappropriate medication usage, and the illegal selling of pharmaceuticals in addition to ADR monitoring. Systems must adapt in order to successfully handle these intricate safety issues.
- **Public Health Versus Pharmaceutical Industry Economic Growth:** Safety monitoring during clinical trials and post-marketing surveillance need to be improved because the pharmaceutical industry may have flaws and competing interests when it comes to addressing drug safety issues.
- **Monitoring of Established Products:** The generic pharmaceutical industry has yet to properly accept its obligation to oversee the security of its goods on a worldwide scale. It is a common misconception that generic pharmaceuticals are always safe, especially when they interfere with other prescriptions. Even though this industry provides the greatest amount of necessary medications, safety oversight still needs to be strengthened.
- **Attitudes and perceptions to benefit and harm:** The way that medications are utilized has changed due to changes in attitudes on their advantages and disadvantages. Patients, healthcare professionals, and the general public have all reacted differently to these changes. It has taken a while for the serious harm caused by medications, especially drug-induced illnesses, to be recognized as a serious public health concern.
- **Outcomes and Impact:** Regulations, business, and health experts are all under more scrutiny as public concern over the safety of medications grows. Expanding pharmacovigilance research is necessary improve public trust and promote more accountability. The main goals should be to manage drug-related disorders, optimize treatment, and lessen the negative effects of medicine by giving patients and healthcare professionals useful information. (35,36,37)

Future Prospects

Fig 6: Pharmacovigilance Activities⁽⁴³⁾

Pharmacovigilance (PV) has a bright future ahead of it. PV systems that are able to identify novel adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and direct regulatory actions to safeguard public health will be developed. It is essential to integrate active post-marketing surveillance approaches and improve the completeness and quality of data on serious events. The goal of PV should be to identify specific risk factors and involve patients and healthcare providers in the reporting process. Better PV procedures will facilitate better decision-making and safety monitoring. These procedures include the incorporation of Good Pharmacovigilance Practices (GPP) and sophisticated tools for data analysis and visualization. PV effectiveness will be further increased by transparency and consumer participation in reporting. ^(38,39)

Conclusion:

Pharmacovigilance serves as a cornerstone in the fight against drug-related adverse events by meticulously tracking and evaluating the safety of medications throughout their existence. It aims to ensure that the therapeutic benefits of drugs significantly surpass their risks. For this system to be truly effective, it relies heavily on the proactive reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) by healthcare professionals—a practice that remains underused despite its critical importance. The involvement of the public in reporting ADRs and providing feedback can substantially reinforce regulatory decisions and enhance drug safety, as illustrated by the success of India's Pharmacovigilance Programme (PvPI). By embracing global standards and focusing on patient-centered care and education, pharmacovigilance can not only foster greater public confidence but also advance the overall effectiveness of healthcare systems.

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